

Articles series, part 3: Tolerances in implant dentistry. Effects of misfit on the multiunit abutments bridge performance, novel numerical model approach for better understanding

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Abstract

The multiunit abutment usage had an increased implementation recently. It had many protocols and witnessed many improvements. It its manufactured using multiple technique. In this paper we had presented a model that is highlighting the effect of the highly possible misfit

Keywords: Multiunit abutment, Tolerances, dental CAD CAM, milling machine, Turning machine

Introduction

There is a raising trend toward the implementation of the multiunit abutments in the prosthetic restoration of the dental implants obviating the need for the cemented restorations. The cementation of the multiunit abutments parts where only one system had an intraoral method and in all of the other remaining systems are done extraorally. The production has uncalculated tolerances as in all the production processes of the implant systems themselves.

These tolerances are occurring in all of the 3 axes of the coordination systems (in the 3-dimensional manner as in the case of milling machines not in a 2-dimensional manner as in the turning machining). We should be careful in the evaluation of these production methods. We now want to represent a model with small tolerances. We have tolerances due to

- the effect of the scan bodies or data acquisition (1). Even with the implementation of the photogrammetry technology we still have tolerances that affect the quality of the data
- due to the production process itself whether it is milling, casting, sintering.... etc. (2)

The misfit of the multiunit abutments will result in disturbance of the loads within the model (3). This will affect the setting of the bridge as well as the loading during functioning. In reality misfit will lead to at least one of the multiunit abutments of the bridge will not have intimate contacts between the components or even there is no contacts in multiple components (4). In this paper we want to investigate a numerical model of all on 4, with just 1 multiunit abutment having a misfit. In this model we want to simulate just the tightening of the connecting screw.

The addition of the functional load will be done in a separate paper if Almighty God will

We had raised the upper part of the multiunit abutment by 10 microns and rotated it by 0.5 degrees which in almost always far away from the ability of the devices used to manufacture the multiunit abutments prosthesis. In the case of multiunit abutment, we had 2 types of misfits

- inclination of the upper part of the multiunit abutment where contact will be in point to surface
- the upper part of multiunit abutment is not in contact with the lower part

The tightening of the inclined abutment will try to rotate the upper part of the multiunit abutment due to the effect of the connecting screw.

Figure 1 Careful inspection of many cases published on the social platform will show that the misfit between the multiunit abutment components is evident

Figure 2 These photos indicate much higher gaps than those assumed in our current research

Even when the surgeon decides to place 6 implants the real contact might be just in 3 implants, but sadly even the implant with contacts will be in inclined not direct fit. The contact between the fitted multiunit abutment and the other abutment should be always considered in this context.

Methods

We had tested a numerical model of a generic implant. The implant had been modeled and tested inside of the SolidWorks environment. The properties had been same as the previous models in our previous papers.

Figure 3 The height of the bone analogue is 20 mm with cylindrical extrusion in the back to get more realistic condition

Fixation of the model base will give highly unrealistic stiff model

Figure 4 The implants relative position is clear

Figure 5 The offsetted model is clear in the term of offset and inclination

Figure 6 The dimensions of the models are apparent

Figure 7 The comparison between the fully seated and offsetted inclined abutment is clear

We had studied this condition of just tightening of the connecting screw as the addition of the occlusal force will exaggerate the corrosion and deformation that is already happening in the assembly. As we said, another condition is highly recommended that is the tightened of the connecting screw with occlusal forces as this is the most detrimental force we might face.

To demonstrate the importance of the bridge material used we had used 2 variations

- bridge manufactured from PMMA
- bridge manufactured from Titanium

Results and discussions

Any misfit in a single unit will not be noticed easily the usage of the multi-unit abutment. This shades the light on how we are had been deceived commercially by the marketing pressure. This also highlight how 3 implants could hold a long bridge while the surgeon had placed 6 or 8 implants.

All the next models are of the best fitness

Figure 8 The displacement criteria are apparent. This is a PMMA bridge

Figure 9 The displacement criteria are apparent. This is a PMMA bridge

Figure 10 Perfect fit PMMA bridge X displacement

Figure 11 Perfect fit Titanium bridge X displacement

Figure 12 Perfect fit PMMA bridge second principal stresses indicating the higher shear inside of the bridge in comparison to the Titanium bridge below.

The design of the abutment is simple like a hollowed tube with protruding shelf that will be pressed downward when the connecting screw is tightened

Figure 13 Perfect fit Titanium bridge second principal stresses

Figure 14 another view of the 2nd principal stress of the PMMA bridge best fit

Figure 15 Another view of the best fit titanium bridge

Figure 16 Another view of the perfect fit strain PMMA bridge

Figure 17 Another view of the perfect fit titanium bridge

Figure 18 Contact pressure of the PMMA bridge

Figure 19 Contact pressure of the Titanium bridge

Figure 20 Another representation of the contact pressure of the PMMA bridge

Figure 21 Another representation of the contact pressure of the Titanium bridge

All the next models are of the best fitness

Figure 22 Displacement of the misfitted model with PMMA bridge. The displacement within the bridge is apparent

Figure 23 The less displacement in the case of the Titanium bridge is apparent

Figure 24 X displacement of the PMMA bridge. The rotation is clearly evident in the bridge whing is higher than the Titanium bridge. The highest values had not been checked as we want to emphasize the importance of the pattern of the deformation rather than revealing a less valuable criterion.

Figure 25 To compare the internal rotation of the upper component in the case of the misfit in a single unit we had brought side by side X field of displacement in the case of PMMA bridge where the difference are clear

Figure 26 X displacement of the Titanium bridge

Figure 27 Strain of the PMMA bridge

Figure 28 Strain of the Titanium bridge

Figure 29 Contact pressure of the PMMA bridge with single unit misfit

Figure 30 Contact pressure of the titanium pressure bridge

Figure 31 2nd principal stress of the PMMA bridge with the single misfitted unit. The deformation extends deep inside the implant

Figure 32 2nd principal stress of the Titanium bridge.

More remote deformation in the implants at the periphery is apparent in the case of titanium bridge with single misfitted unit

Figure 33 Strain of the PMMA bridge

Figure 34 Strain of the Titanium bridge with single misfitted unit

Figure 35 the comparison between the strain in the case of Titanium bridge is apparent when we shift from the perfect fitted model to the model with single misfitted unit

Figure 36 Contact pressure of the PMMA bridge

Figure 37 Contact pressure of the Titanium bridge

Figure 38 Titanium bridge. This is the last model with single misfit but flat as we cut 50 microns evenly from single unit

Figure 39 Titanium bridge. This is the last model with single misfit but flat as we cut 50 microns evenly

Figure 40 The 100 microns misfit will never end in contact

Figure 41 Theoretically if you exert 1000 N force as tightening of the connecting screw you will not get contact in the case of 100 microns misfit

Figure 42 Theoretically, when you are reaching contact in the case of the 100 microns gap you will end by

In the previous models we should emphasize the importance of noticing these issues

- deformation of the bridge that will occur during connecting screw tightening
- contact condition of the multiple parts
- tolerances of the production

All modularities in the implant dentistry should be approached carefully. This is well documented in the orthopedics surgeries (5) All the previous models are of the misfitted one of the 4 multiunit abutment where more mistiness could be happened in different forms.

References

References

1. *Comparison of the accuracy of different impression procedures in case of multiple and angulated implants : Accuracy of impressions in multiple and angulated implants.* **Richi MW, Kurtulmus-Yilmaz S, Ozan O.** s.l. : Head Face Med. , 2020.
2. *Repositioning accuracy of the implant- and abutment-level prosthetic components used in conventional and digital workflows.* **Vygandas Rutkūnas, Vytautas Bilius, Julius Dirsė, Marta Revilla-León, Marius Rimašauskas, Łukasz Zadrożny, Rita Trumpaitė-Vanagienė.** s.l. : , Journal of Dentistry, , 2024.
3. *Evaluation of accuracy of complete-arch multiple-unit abutment-level dental implant impressions using different impression and splinting materials.* . **Buzayan M, Baig MR, Yunus N.** s.l. : Int J Oral Maxillofac Implants. , 2013.
4. *Effect of Angulation Between Multi-Unit Abutments on Accuracy of Photogrammetry Scanning.* **Andejani, Abdulelah.** s.l. : University of Illinois Chicago. Thesis. <https://doi.org/10.25417/uic.29049770.v1>, (2024).
5. *Modularity in Total Hip Arthroplasty: Benefits, Risks, Mechanisms, Diagnosis, and Management.* . **Vierra BM, Blumenthal SR, Amanatullah DF.** s.l. : Orthopedics. , 2017 .
6. *Effect of teeth periodontium presence on the bone physiology against stiffer status after implant placement or teeth ankylosis event. Teeth as jaw weakeners: a pivotal concept in the biomechanics.* **Saadoon, M. Z.** (. s.l. : International Journal of Biomodels and Biosimulations (IJBB), 1(2), 1–33., 2025).
7. *MOHAMMED BODIES' ANALYSIS FEA OF DENTAL IMPLANTS' DESIGN CRITERIA.* **Saadoon, M. Z.** (2020).

Author profile

Mohammed Zahid Saadoon BDS– FKHCMS (Maxillofacial Surgery). During 2014-2024 he was involved in many researches in biomechanics and biomechatronic. He developed many theories in maxillofacial traumatology, craniofacial growth and dental implantology. He developed a unique dental implant system. He has a special interest in mechanical engineering applications in the medical and dental specialties as well as in forensic medicine. He is now working as maxillofacial surgeon in Ashty teaching hospital, largest secondary referral centers in Soran discrete at Kurdistan region / Iraq.